

LET'S ACHIEVE ALL GOALS BY HONORING HUMAN DIGNITY AND
QUALITY EDUCATION!

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Abstract. This article talks about a person's desire to improve personal values, increase their value, realize the value of others, society, time and changes taking place in it. It is analyzed that improving the quality and efficiency of education during the years of independence to the level of modern requirements has become one of the priority directions of state policy.

Keywords: Human dignity, education, quality education, rights and freedom, values, society, national, regional, preschool education.

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"Where there is intelligence, there is greatness, where there is knowledge, there is greatness."

Yusuf Khos Hajib

It is no coincidence that the main attention is focused on education and training in the next address of the President of Uzbekistan to the Oliy Majlis. In fact, quality education is an important factor of sustainable development and progress. At first glance, the forms of values seems to be countless and extremely chaotic. Actually, there is an amazing harmony in humanity, universe, nature and society. A clear example of this is the fact that the word "education" is used the most in the petition. First of all, it was noted that attention should be focused on supporting education, which is the biggest investment for Uzbekistan. The declaration of 2023 as the "year of attention to people and quality education" requires the continuation of reforms in this field.

Forms of value are also corresponding to them in such a harmony, legal connection, general connection. In this case, their classification includes things, events, acts, and processes in nature and society turn up on a certain scale, and value forms appear in connection with them.

In space and time, these objects of value appear as a form of existence, an aspect, a part of reality, the most important aspects of things in the world and the environment. In this sense, it is possible to show the forms of values that are universal, global and regional, as well as depending on a small area or place. In this

case, the dialectic of generality, particularity and individuality appears in the form of the interaction of modern terms "global", "zonal" and "local" objects of value.

Along with the above values, universal human values in the society are also important for the existence of the society and people's life. Their categories related to society, its structure, social units and forms of social consciousness which can be shown. For example, national, specific to the structure of society, class, race, etc., or depending on the forms of social consciousness: political, legal, moral, religious, as well as on the main areas of society: economic, social, cultural, spiritual. Differences between forms of social value are not absolute, but relative. There are no insurmountable boundaries between them.

If this is clear, there are many cases of using it as a general name or term for cultural and spiritual phenomena, customs, traditions, etc. In everyday communication, many people are used to calling something, action, event, characteristic, etc., which has value. But the essence of each word, term and concept and there is a qualitative limit to the content. There is no need to demand from this or that concept a scope that does not fit this content. After all, it is very good that the concept of value has become popular and popular. But use it in a broader sense or in cases where it is not necessary using it can blur the meaning of this concept, turn the quality limit that expresses its essence into a mirage, and reduce its value.

There are sayings of among people: "There is no value without value!", "Value without value is like a mirage." It is for this reason that we should highly value such values as independence, great future, patriotism, humanitarianism, democracy, rule of law, which are the highest expressions of the current period of our country's development. The first of them is the main reality of the development of Uzbekistan, which has declared independence, on the threshold of the new century, the second is our highest dream-ideal in the future, and the others are our fundamental values that determine the social and spiritual principles of our society.

Independence made issues related to human value, interests and needs urgent. The value of a person is also seen in his social characteristics, his activities in society, his attitude towards others and the environment, his maturity, his mastery of social characteristics and his ability to manifest them in his spiritual form. The process of the human child becoming a person, realizing his value and the value of others takes many years.

In general, today, when the current generation of the human race is approaching the third millennium, there is an increased need to apply the universal criteria of the philosophy of appreciation in the whole world. Unfortunately, if the human race had prioritized value and dignity from the first time it lived on our planet, wouldn't the modern landscape of the Earth have taken a completely different shape, wouldn't

humanity have faced universal problems such as ecological crises, the threat of war, and moral decline?

To date, humanity has again realized that value and dignity are extremely necessary to preserve the harmony of nature and the human race. It is no coincidence that the last five years of the 20th century and the first five years at the beginning of the 21st century were declared by the UN as the "Decade of Human Rights", and the human society is moving into the new millennium to stabilize universal values. Activities related to the realization of human interests and rights, the priority of the universal principles of appreciation in Uzbekistan are becoming a component of the movement to strengthen the general cooperation in this regard throughout the world.

The whole life of the person consists of the process of improving personal values, perfecting one's value, striving to understand the value of others, society, time and the changes taking place in it. In order to realize the value of one's own person and others, the spiritual image and world of a person formed during his maturity should serve goodness, have high social qualities, and he should be educated to the extent that he understands the essence and purpose of life. In this sense, Socrates' "know thyself!" - slogan is very important.

The value of a person is manifested in the dialectical relationship with the time he lives in, the processes in it, social and historical conditions. The demands of the environment and the time shape and refine the value of the individual, and he himself moves towards a deeper understanding of how his value is related to his personal requirements, needs and goals. Values allow young people to gain a deeper understanding of the meaning of life, to use the rules of society correctly, to adapt their behavior to the requirements of these moral criteria. In the current period, it is extremely urgent to convey to students and pupils the essence of the processes of appreciation and depreciation, to achieve a correct explanation of the importance of the values declared by independence.

It is extremely important to teach the basics of modern axiology, that is, value science, which is a set of knowledge about the sense of value and appreciation, the category of values, their essence, content, and forms of manifestation, in the education and formation of young people, especially students and pupils, as representatives of a spiritually mature generation. For this reason, one of the main criteria of educational effectiveness is the use of knowledge fields that summarize the achievements of the entire humanity in terms of values.

"When will attention be paid to a person?" Education, education, education and more education. If there is education, if there is knowledge, the quality will change. If there is no education, if the quality does not change, the attention will not change" confirms the actual topic of today. In general, in recent years special attention has been paid to the issues of education, especially higher education. In Uzbekistan,

certain works have been carried out to improve the higher education system, to ensure adequate coverage at each stage of education, to strengthen the material and technical base of educational organizations, and to create conditions for continuing education. As a result, the number of higher education institutions has reached 198, the number of non-state higher education institutions is increasing. Thanks to these reforms, the coverage of higher education in the country was increased from 9% to 38%.

In fact, our most priceless wealth is our creative people, our prayerful parents, our humble generation, isn't it?

We are trying to create all the necessary conditions for everyone living in this country to live a peaceful and happy life, to be in good health, to get a good education, to support their families, and there is no stopping from this path.

If the reputation of teachers and trainers is "put in place", if quality changes are made in schools, pre-school educational organizations and universities, then the two-three-fold change of all actions will definitely give a positive result. "Achievements will be ours, only knowledge is needed. We need knowledge, no matter what you say, each of us should look back and never forget what great ancestors we are.

The President proposed naming 2023 as "Year of attention to people and quality education". Of course, this proposal was welcomed by our compatriots. Giving such a name to the year will make the life of our people more prosperous and meaningful, and in our country where great scholars like Imam Bukhari, Imam Termizi, Imam Moturidi, Ahmad-al Farghani, who made a worthy contribution to world knowledge, have grown up, all the strength and opportunities are mobilized so that their successors will also mature. I believe that it is a sign that large-scale reforms will be implemented in order to glorify human dignity.

Well, where there is no knowledge, there will be backwardness, ignorance and, of course, going astray. As the sages of the East say, "The greatest wealth is intelligence and knowledge, the greatest inheritance is a good upbringing, and the greatest poverty is ignorance!" In the words of our head of state, improving the quality of education is the only correct way of development of New Uzbekistan.

Acquiring modern knowledge, becoming the owner of true enlightenment and high culture is becoming a constant vital need. It is permissible to admit that knowledge and spirituality are of incomparable importance in human life, moreover, we can achieve our great goal of turning our Heavenly Motherland into a developed country by further improving the knowledge and spirituality of our people and by implementing rapid reforms in all areas.

In the center of the state policy conducted in Uzbekistan, the priority task is to ensure the interests of people. Honoring human dignity means ensuring the rights and freedoms and legal interests of every person living in our country.

In recent years, high attention has been paid to human capital in our country, which is gaining historical significance. Therefore, human capital is the level of a person's willingness to benefit himself, his country, and his people.

Also, in the "Year of attention to people and quality education", it is even more gratifying that the volume of investments directed to the human factor - upbringing, education, knowledge, health care and well-being of life - is increasing.

The bright future, prosperity and stability of our country and its rightful place among the countries of the world are undoubtedly in the hands of today's youth who possess innovative knowledge, in other words, possess human capital. For this reason, our state is taking the most important steps in youth education. It will definitely pay off in the near future! In the years of independence, raising the quality and efficiency of education to the level of modern requirements became one of the priority directions of the state policy.

Today, the rapid development of science, technology and production requires raising the quality of education in all educational institutions to a new level in terms of content.

This, in turn, imposes higher responsibilities and tasks on each system employee, especially teachers. Because there is one undeniable fact - all the efforts made by the teacher's work will ultimately show their results in the good knowledge and good morals of the teachers. Therefore, pedagogues are required to work conscientiously, to be responsible for our bright future, and to respond appropriately to the high attention shown.

Therefore, the quality and efficiency of education depends primarily on quality education. Quality education, in the vernacular, depends on a good teacher, teacher and educator.

Humans have appeared, education has appeared. Education has appeared, and the qualities and requirements of teachers have increased. It is worth noting that behind the word "good" there is always positivity, the concept of achieving an effective result. That is, the goodness of good teachers is explained by their high-achieving students and the large number of students who have found their place in society.

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